

TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN CONTENT AND PEDAGOGY IN CLASSROOMS AS EFFECTING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

Jose Calasanz Julysse D. Tabia¹, Josephine L. Chavez², Glory Ann C. Doncoy³
Argie B. Doncoy⁴

¹ Graduate School, St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Dipolog City, Philippines

² Graduate School, St. Vincent's College Incorporated, Dipolog City, Philippines

³ Department of Education, Zamboanga del Norte Division, Dipolog City, Philippines

⁴ Department of Education, Zamboanga del Norte Division, Dipolog City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252016>

Abstract

This study described the technology integration in content and pedagogy and students' affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement. This study also examined the impact of integrating technology into content and pedagogy on student engagement. Both descriptive and correlational designs were utilized, with a questionnaire serving as a primary instrument for data collection. The research sample was taken from the Grade VI teachers and Grade VI pupils of Ponot District. A total of 26 teachers and 171 students took part in this study. It was revealed that the teachers extensively integrated technology into their teaching methods and subject matter and the students were actively engaged in classrooms. The teachers were knowledgeable in communicating the lessons to students through technologies that supported their learning and deployed technological tools alongside pedagogy in ways that were appropriate to the development of the lesson. Additionally, the study found a notable correlation between the degree of technology integration in the classroom and the level of student engagement. Moreover, the utilization of technology by teachers in delivering lessons and their expertise in establishing an effective learning environment positively influenced student engagement.

Keywords: *Technology Integration in Content and Pedagogy; Student Affective, Behavioral, and Cognitive Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of technology in classrooms has become more widespread as educators acknowledge its potential to improve the delivery of subject matter and pedagogical practices. This research aims to explore the impact of technology integration on student engagement in the classroom. Student engagement is a critical factor in promoting effective learning outcomes, as it encompasses students' active participation, motivation, and interest in the learning process. By examining the relationship between technology integration, content, pedagogy, and student engagement, this study seeks to provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers in designing effective instructional strategies.

Ranosa (2020) asserts that the Department of Education (DepEd) introduced the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, which incorporates the use of technology in the curriculum. Subsequently, the DepEd has implemented various initiatives to promote the integration of technology in classrooms to get the students engaged and improve learning outcomes. According to a study conducted by Puentedura (2006), technology integration can be categorized into four levels: substitution, augmentation, modification, and redefinition. Each level represents a different degree of technology's impact on teaching and learning. The study found that higher levels of technology integration, such as modification and redefinition, were associated with increased student engagement and improved learning outcomes.

Furthermore, research by Means et al. (2010) suggests that technology integration in content and pedagogy can enhance student engagement by providing interactive and personalized learning experiences. The study found that technology-enabled instructional practices, such as multimedia presentations, online discussions, and virtual simulations, fostered higher levels of student engagement compared to traditional teaching methods. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of technology integration in promoting student engagement may vary depending on various factors, including the quality of instructional design, teacher training, and the availability of resources. Therefore, this research will also explore the challenges and barriers faced by educators in effectively integrating technology into their classrooms.

While there has been a growing body of research on the impact of technology integration on student engagement, there is still a significant research gap regarding the specific effects of technology integration in content and pedagogy on student engagement in classrooms. Existing studies have primarily focused on the general benefits of technology integration or have examined specific technologies in isolation. However, there is a lack of comprehensive research that investigates the combined effects of technology integration in content and pedagogy on student engagement. Additionally, there is a need for more empirical studies that explore the potential challenges and limitations of technology integration in relation to student engagement. By addressing this research gap, this study aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of how technology integration in content and pedagogy can effectively enhance student engagement in classrooms.

In conclusion, this research aims to investigate the impact of technology integration in content and pedagogy on student engagement in classrooms. By examining the relationship between these variables, this study seeks to provide valuable insights for

educators and policymakers in promoting effective instructional practices that enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the technology integration in content and pedagogy in classrooms as effecting student engagement.

This study answers the following questions:

1. What is the extent of technology integration in classrooms as effecting student engagement along:
 - 1.2 content; and
 - 1.2 pedagogy?
2. What is the level of students' engagement along;
 - 2.1 behavioral;
 - 2.2 cognitive; and
 - 2.3 affective?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of technology integration in classrooms as effecting student engagement and the level of students' engagement?

METHODOLOGY

Both descriptive and correlational research design with a questionnaire as the primary tool for data collection. Descriptive analysis was used to describe the extent of teachers' technology integration in content and pedagogy and the level of students' engagement. Correlational analysis was used to establish the relationships between the teachers' technology integration and the pupils' engagement in the classroom. This study used twenty-six (26) classroom teachers who were randomly selected from the ten (10) schools of Ponot district, schools division of Zamboanga del Norte.

The researcher utilized the questionnaire for computer literacy adapted from the study of Hosseini (2012) which determined the teachers' technology integration in content and pedagogy in classrooms. This used the Likert scale rating from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The questionnaire for students' engagement in terms of affective, behavioral and cognitive domains was adapted from the study of Defino (2019). This used the Likert scale rating from 1 (Rarely) to 4 (Always). The questionnaires were pre-tested to non-respondents to get the reliability and validity. The reliability and validity of the instruments were found high.

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data collected for this study:

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the extent of teachers' technology integration in content and pedagogy and students' engagement.

Spearman-Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationship between the teachers' technology integration in content and pedagogy and students' engagement.

The data were analyzed using MS Excel and Jamovi v. 2.3.19. The relationship was tested using a .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms along Content is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms along Content

Items	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I know about technologies that I can use for understanding (the particular content)	3.46	.508	High
2. I know how to use specific software and Web sites about (the particular content).	3.15	.613	Moderate
3. I can find and evaluate the resources that I need for (the particular content)	3.12	.326	Moderate
4. I can use technology for presenting (the particular content).	3.19	.491	Moderate
5. I can use technology tools and resources for managing and communicating information of (the particular content).	3.35	.629	High
6. I can teach lessons that appropriately using (the particular content) technologies.	3.19	.491	Moderate
7. I can select technologies to use in my classroom that enhance what I teach.	3.46	.508	High
8. I can choose technologies that enhance the learning of (the particular content) for a lesson.	3.54	.508	High
9. I can evaluate and select new information resources and technological innovations based on their appropriateness to specific tasks in (the particular content).	3.19	.402	Moderate
10. I can use (the particular content)-specific tools (e.g., software, simulation, environmental probes, graphing calculators, exploratory environments, Web tools) to support learning and research.	3.23	.430	Moderate
Grand Weighted Mean	3.29	.510	High
1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree/Very Low	1.76 – 2.50 Disagree/Low		
2.51 – 3.25 Agree/Moderate	3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/High		

The Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms along Pedagogy is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms along Pedagogy

Items	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. I can choose technologies that enhance the teaching approaches for a lesson.	3.38	.496	High
2. I can choose technologies that enhance students' learning for a lesson.	3.35	.485	High
3. I am thinking critically about how to use technology in my classroom.	3.46	.508	High
4. I can adapt the use of the technologies that I am learning about to different teaching activities.	3.42	.504	High
5. My teacher education program has caused me to think more deeply about how technology could influence the teaching approaches I use in my classroom	3.42	.504	High
6. I can use technology resources to facilitate higher order thinking skills, including problem solving critical thinking, decision-making, knowledge and creative thinking.	3.31	.471	High
7. I can use technology tools and information resources to increase productivity.	3.46	.508	High
8. I can infuse technology to strategies of teaching.	3.42	.504	High
9. I can use technology for more collaboration and communication among students and with teacher too.	3.54	.508	High
10. I know how to use technology to facilitate academic learning.	3.27	.452	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.40	.492	High
1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree/Very Low	1.76 – 2.50 Disagree/Low		
2.51 – 3.25 Agree/Moderate	3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/High		

The Summary of the Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Summary of the Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Content	3.29	.510	High
Pedagogy	3.40	.492	High
Grand Mean	3.35	.504	High
1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree/Very Low		1.76 – 2.50 Disagree/Low	
2.51 – 3.25 Agree/Moderate		3.26 – 4.00 Strongly Agree/High	

The Level of Students' Behavioral Engagement is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The Level of Students' Behavioral Engagement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Asked questions in class or contributed to class discussion.	3.25	.742	Engaged
2. Raising my hand in class.	3.05	.863	Engaged
3. Participating in or small group discussions.	3.23	.712	Engaged
4. Doing all the homework problems.	3.36	.794	Engaged
5. Coming to class every day.	3.63	.633	Highly Engaged
6. Taking good notes in class.	3.37	.743	Engaged
7. Getting a good grade.	3.10	.809	Engaged
8. Staying up on the readings.	3.29	.795	Engaged
9. Received timely written or oral feedback from teachers on your academic performance.	3.12	.900	Engaged
10. Come to class with completing readings or assignments	2.66	1.138	Engaged
11. Making sure to study on a regular basis.	3.22	.788	Engaged
12. Doing well on a test.	3.14	.785	Engaged
Grand Weighted Mean	3.20	.866	Engaged
1.00 – 1.50 Rarely/Less Engaged		1.51 – 2.50 Sometimes/Moderately Engaged	
2.51 – 3.50 Often/Engaged		3.51 – 4.00 Almost Always/Highly Engaged	

The Level of Students' Cognitive Engagement is shown in Table 5.

Table 5*The Level of Students' Cognitive Engagement*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Made a class presentation	3.04	.821	Engaged
2. Prepared assignment ahead of time and checked it before submitting it.	2.95	.880	Engaged
3. Worked on a paper or project that required integrating ideas or information from previous sources.	2.92	.819	Engaged
4. Put together ideas or concepts from different courses when completing assignments or during class discussion.	2.95	.792	Engaged
5. Used an electronic medium (Facebook, group chat, Internet, instant messaging, etc.) to discuss or complete an assignment.	2.80	1.068	Engaged
6. Discussed ideas from your readings or classes with faculty members outside the class.	2.65	.930	Engaged
7. Putting forth effort.	3.08	.847	Engaged
8. Used messenger or text message to communicate with an instructor.	2.44	1.107	Moderately Engaged
9. Discussed grades or assignments with teachers.	2.76	1.009	Engaged
10. Work harder than you thought you could do to meet a teacher's standards or expectations.	3.10	.824	Engaged
11. Discussed ideas from your readings or classes with others outside of class (students, family members, co-workers, etc)	2.89	.843	Engaged
12. Going to the teacher's office hours to review assignments of tests, or to ask questions.	2.39	1.002	Moderately Engaged
13. Thinking about the lesson between class meetings.	2.78	.878	Engaged
14. Finding ways to make the lesson interesting to me.	2.95	.990	Engaged
15. Looking over class notes between classes to make sure I understand the materials.	2.91	.975	Engaged
16. Applying the lessons I've learned to my life.	3.06	.899	Engaged
17. Trying to find ways to apply the lessons and knowledge to my life.	2.99	.927	Engaged
Grand Weighted Mean	2.86	.942	Engaged

1.00 – 1.50 Rarely/Less Engaged
 2.51 – 3.50 Often/Engaged

1.51 – 2.50 Sometimes/Moderately Engaged
 3.51 – 4.00 Almost Always/Highly Engaged

The Level of Students' Affective Engagement is shown in Table 6.

Table 6

The Level of Students' Cognitive Engagement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Included diverse perspective in class discussions or writing assignments.	3.15	.764	Engaged
2. Worked with other students on projects during class.	2.75	1.073	Engaged
3. Worked with classmates outside or class to prepare class assignments.	3.01	.894	Engaged
4. Tutored or taught other students paid or voluntary.	2.60	1.054	Engaged
5. Participated in a community-based project as part of a regular course.	2.82	1.020	Engaged
6. Had serious conversations with students who are very different from you in terms of their religious, political opinions, or personal values.	2.89	.961	Engaged
7. Really desiring to learn the materials.	3.26	.801	Engaged
8. Being confident that I can learn and do well in the class.	3.27	.726	Engaged
9. Having fun in class.	3.48	.754	Engaged
10. Worked with faculty members on activities other than course work.	2.92	.864	Engaged
11. Talked about career plans with a faculty member or adviser	2.98	1.003	Engaged
Grand Weighted Mean	3.01	.937	Engaged
1.00 – 1.50 Rarely/Less Engaged	1.51 – 2.50 Sometimes/Moderately Engaged		
2.51 – 3.50 Often/Engaged	3.51 – 4.00 Almost Always/Highly Engaged		

The Summary of the Level of Students' Engagement is shown in Table 7.

Table 7

The Summary of the Level of Students' Engagement

Domains	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Behavioral	3.20	.866	Engaged
Cognitive	2.86	.942	Engaged
Affective	3.01	.937	Engaged
Grand Mean	3.02	.927	Engaged
1.00 – 1.75 Very Rarely/Less Engaged	1.76 – 2.50 Sometimes/Moderately Engaged		
2.51 – 3.25 Often/Engaged	3.26 – 4.00 Almost Always/Highly Engaged		

The Relationship Between the Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms and the Level of Students' Engagement is shown in Table 8.

Table 8

The Relationship Between the Extent of Technology Integration in Classrooms and the Level of Students' Engagement

Variables	Computed ρ	P-Value	Interpretation
Content and Students' Engagement	.801	.000	High Positive Correlation/Significant
Pedagogy and Students' Engagement	.322	.000	Moderate Positive Correlation/ Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the extent of technology integration along content. The table shows the items, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. The summarized responses of teachers got a grand weighted mean 3.29 and standard deviation .510 that described the extent of technology integration along content as high. The teachers highly integrated technology into the lesson to enhance the students' learning experience. They selected and utilized technology tools that are relevant and appropriate for the subject matter being taught. Through technology, the teachers create a more engaging and interactive learning experience for students. The result above is consistent to the study of Mishra, et al. (2009) who argued that effective technology integration in education should focus on the content being taught rather than solely on the technology itself. They propose the Technological

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which emphasizes the integration of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge.

Table 2 presents the extent of technology integration along pedagogy. The table shows the items, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. The summed-up data about technology integration along pedagogy produced a grand weighted mean 3.40 and standard deviation .492 depicted that the teachers were knowledgeable on how to appropriately use technology in the teaching-learning process to benefit students across diverse subject matter. The teachers effectively use technology-based teaching and learning tools that improved learning outcomes. They intentionally selected and utilized technology tools that support and enhance their chosen pedagogical approaches. The above result corroborated to the study of Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2013) as it emphasizes the importance of aligning technology integration with pedagogical goals and strategies. It suggests that technology should be used as a tool to enhance and transform teaching and learning, rather than simply substituting traditional methods.

Table 3 presents the summary of the extent of technology integration. The table shows the indicator, mean, standard deviation, grand mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. The collective ratings of teachers revealed that the extent of technology integration as effecting student engagement were high with a grand mean 3.35 and standard deviation .504. This entailed that teachers were knowledgeable in communicating the lessons to students through technologies that supported their learning and deployed technological tools alongside pedagogy in ways that were appropriate to the development of the lesson. The teachers were intentional and strategic in using technology tools and resources to enhance both the delivery of educational content and the pedagogical approaches employed in teaching and learning. The result above corroborated the study of Voogt et al. (2018). The study highlights the need for technology integration to go beyond simply using digital tools and resources. It suggests that technology should be integrated in a way that promotes active learning, collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. The authors argue that effective technology integration involves designing learning environments that leverage technology to create authentic and meaningful learning experiences.

Table 4 presents the level of students' behavioral engagement. The table shows the indicator, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, and implication. According to the findings, the level of students' behavioral engagement was described as "engaged" with a grand weighted mean 3.20 and standard deviation .866. The students' believed that technologies in classroom somehow stimulate their interest to get engaged. Through integrating technology in classrooms by their teachers, the students' learning experience were enhanced as these technologies provide more learning opportunities to them. The extent to which students actively participate, interact, and remain focused during the learning process when technology tools and resources are incorporated into their educational experiences is deemed necessary. The above result corroborated the study of Kay and Lauricella (2020) titled "Examining the Effects of Classroom Technology Use on Students' Behavioral Engagement: A Systematic Review." The study found that

technology integration in the classroom can have positive effects on students' behavioral engagement. It highlighted that interactive and collaborative technology tools, such as educational apps, online platforms, and multimedia resources, can enhance students' active participation and motivation.

Table 5 presents the level of students' cognitive engagement. The table shows the indicator, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, and implication. The students' rating along this dimension lead to a grand weighted mean 2.86 and standard deviation .942 which pointed out the level of students' cognitive engagement were "engaged". This suggested that the students were willing to exert effort necessary to comprehend the concepts and master difficult skills to improve their performance. The extent to which students actively and intellectually participate in the learning process when technology tools and resources are incorporated into their educational experiences is essential to their learning. The above result corroborated with the findings of Schmid et al. (2020) titled "Effects of Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments on Students' Cognitive Engagement: A Systematic Literature Review." The study found that technology integration in the classroom can have positive effects on students' cognitive engagement. It highlighted that technology tools, such as simulations, virtual reality, multimedia resources, and online platforms, can enhance students' critical thinking skills, promote active information processing, and facilitate knowledge construction.

Table 6 presents the level of students' affective engagement. The table shows the indicator, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, and implication. The students' rating in this dimension found a grand weighted mean 3.01 and standard deviation .937 which described the level of students' affective engagement as "engaged". Through the teachers' use of technology to support learning, the students were willing to do the work and even learn to collaborate with their peers. The use of learning technologies lead to effective instructional practices that made students to positively react to learning environment and peers. The emotional and motivational aspects of student involvement and investment in the learning process when technology tools and resources are incorporated into their educational experiences must be considered.

The above result is consistent with the findings of Banitt, et al. (2013) as it revealed that there is an increase in student engagement as well as improved student enjoyment and enthusiasm for lessons involving technology when compared to traditional, parallel lessons.

Table 7 presents the summary of the level of students' engagement. The table shows the dimension, mean, standard deviation, grand mean, and interpretation. The overall assessment of students indicated that they were actively engaged across all three dimensions of engagement. Furthermore, the grand mean 3.02 and standard deviation .927 indicated that the students were actively engaged when technologies were integrated in classrooms. Technology integration in classrooms enhanced creativity and critical thinking skills of students, fosters collaboration, and helped the students to connect with their teachers and peers. The level of active participation, motivation, and focus that students exhibit during the learning process when technology tools and resources are

incorporated into their educational experiences was improved. This corroborated with the findings of Schindler et al. (2017) in the study “Computer-based technology and student engagement: a critical review of the literature”. It revealed that computer-based technology influences student engagement and has far-reaching effects across multiple types and indicators of student engagement, suggesting that technology should be considered a factor that influences student engagement in existing models.

Table 8 presents the relationship between the extent of technology integration in classroom and the level of students’ engagement. The table shows the variables, computed ρ , P-value, and interpretation. The computed ρ -values .801 for Content and Students’ Engagement and .122 for Pedagogy and Students’ Engagement got P-values that were less than .05 level of significance. This means that there was a significant relationship between the extent of technology integration in classroom and the level of students’ engagement. This entailed that the teachers’ use of technology in the lesson delivery and knowledge in creating an effective learning environment enhanced students’ engagement. In the context of the TPACK theory, this suggests that when teachers have a strong understanding of the subject matter, utilize effective pedagogical strategies, and possess knowledge about standard technologies, they are able to enhance the teaching and learning process, resulting in increased student engagement and participation in the classroom.

The above result corroborated the findings of Dublar (2023) to identify the impact of emerging technology integration on the knowledge and skills acquisition of K-12 students in the Philippines. It was found that technology integration has resulted in improved student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The teachers highly integrated technology in content and pedagogy in classrooms. They were knowledgeable in communicating the lessons to students through technologies that supported their learning and deployed technological tools alongside pedagogy in ways that were appropriate to the development of the lesson. The students were actively engaged in classrooms. When technology was integrated in the delivery of instruction, it enhanced creativity and critical thinking skills of students, fosters collaboration, and helped the students to connect with their teachers and peers. Furthermore, the teachers’ use of technology in the lesson delivery and knowledge in creating an effective learning environment enhanced students’ engagement.

Recommendations

- Through the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:
1. Teachers should communicate the learning objectives to students and demonstrate how technology integration supports those objectives.
 2. Teachers should incorporate interactive and collaborative technology tools that promote active participation and collaboration among students.

3. Teachers should provide clear instructions and scaffolding to support students in effectively using technology tools.
4. Teachers should create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students feel comfortable and encouraged to explore and experiment with technology.
5. Further research could explore the specific factors that contribute to moderate positive correlation between integration of technology in pedagogy and student engagement despite high technology integration in pedagogy and active student engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) have declared that they do not have any conflicts of interest related to the research, authorship, or publication of this article. The authors conducted the study in accordance with the research ethics protocol. The participants were provided with informed consent before receiving the research questionnaire. The data were handled with the highest level of confidentiality.

Acknowledgements

The authors extend their appreciation to the participants of this study and their school administrators. The authors also acknowledge the anonymous reviewers and editors for their valuable feedback and support in enhancing this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Banitt, Justin; Theis, Sharon; and Van Leeuwe, Lucas. (2013). The Effects of Technology Integration on Student Engagement. Retrieved from Sophia, the St. Catherine University repository website: <https://sophia.stkate.edu/maed/7>
- Delfino, A. P. (2019). Student Engagement and Academic Performance of Students of Partido State University. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 15, 42-55. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1222588.pdf>
- Dublar, Cheryl. (2023). Title: Assessing the Impact of Emerging Technology Integration on Knowledge and Skills Acquisition of K-12 Students in the Philippines: A Systematic Literature Review. 10.13140/RG.2.2.29073.30561.
- Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T. (2013). Removing obstacles to the pedagogical changes required by Jonassen's vision of authentic technology-enabled learning. *Computers & Education*, 64, 175-182.
- Hosseini, Zahra. (2012). Developing an Instrument to Measure Perceived Technology Integration Knowledge of Teachers.
- Kay, R. H., & Lauricella, A. R. (2020). Examining the Effects of Classroom Technology Use on Students' Behavioral Engagement: A Systematic Review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(2), 461-487.
- Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., & Jones, K. (2009). Evaluation of

evidence-based practices in online learning: A meta-analysis and review of online learning studies.

- Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., & Kereluik, K. (2009). The song remains the same: Looking back to the future of educational technology. *TechTrends*, 53(5), 48-53.
- Puntedura, R. R. (2006). Transformation, technology, and education. Retrieved from <http://hippasus.com/resources/tte/>
- Ranosa, R. (2020). The role of ICT in Philippine basic education. *International Journal of Educational Research Review*, 5(1), 9-14.
- Schindler, L.A., Burkholder, G.J., Morad, O.A. et al. Computer-based technology and student engagement: a critical review of the literature. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 14, 25 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0063-0>
- Schmid, R. F., Bernard, R. M., Borokhovski, E., Tamim, R. M., Abrami, P. C., Wade, C. A., ... & Surkes, M. A. (2020). Effects of Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments on Students' Cognitive Engagement: A Systematic Literature Review. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(4), 506-546.
- Voogt, J., Knezek, G., Christensen, R., & Lai, K. W. (2018). Guidelines for Designing Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 23(1), 1-3.